

SUICIDE IS BOTH A SIGNIFICANT PUBLIC HEALTH ISSUE AND THE BIGGEST CAUSE OF DEATH ACROSS THE GLOBE

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Abstract

It should come as no surprise that suicide is both a significant public health issue and the biggest cause of death across the globe. Since this topic requires a great deal more work, it needs to be discussed, even though it is necessary to develop it in the literature (Stevens, 2006). According to the most recent data available, around one million people take their own lives each year, which equates to a suicide rate that is age-standardized and global that is 11.4 per 100,000 population (15.0 for men and 8.0 for women). (Brody, 1995) When viewed through the lens of time, the suicide rate increased by thirty percent across all age groups between the years 2000 and 2016. In addition, considering the prediction made by the WHO that the annual number of suicides will surpass the one million mark within the next 15 years, it is anticipated that the annual number of suicides will climb in the future. As therapists and researchers, it is our responsibility to make every attempt to recognize suicide behavior, intervene with it, and then ultimately prevent it. Primarily, our objective is to further our knowledge by developing an interdisciplinary understanding of the processes, variables, and facilitators that are associated with suicide. (Shain, 2007)

Keywords: *Suicide, Psychology of Suicide, Reasons for Suicide, Suicide in Psychology, Solutions to Suicide*

Introduction

There are a great many factors, both contributing and enabling, that go into the act of suicide, making it an overly complicated and varied occurrence. The combination of several elements, including neurobiology, personal or family history, stressful experiences, and sociocultural environment, might play a role in the decision to take one's own life. Considering that suicide thought, and behavior are among the most violent human actions, a distinct emphasis will be placed on uncovering the underlying psychological processes that may rise to suicidal ideation and conduct. Throughout the last century, we have acknowledged the significance of psychological elements (both individual and societal) to suicide and suicide risk. A variety of models have been presented, primarily highlighting the relationship between predisposing and accelerating variables. (Wasserman, Cheng, & Jiang, 2005)

Throughout the month before to their death, around 45% of persons who died because of suicide consulted a physician without disclosing their suicidal feelings

and thoughts. This statistic is based on the number of people who died by suicide. This conclusion draws attention to the fact that challenges in communication are the primary focus of our investigation into the phenomenon of suicidal conduct. As part of the Israel MSSA (Medically Serious Suicide Attempts) research, (Levi, et al., 2003) and his colleagues demonstrated that bad character, in conjunction with a number of other relevant variables, might make suicide conduct easier to carry out and more deadly.

Suicide in the United States: CC BY-SA¹

There has been a lot of research done on this subject that has altered other significant risk variables. According to Tavakoli et al., who studied the relationship between attentional control and suicidal behavior in a cohort of inpatient adolescents who exhibit acute suicidal behavior compared to healthy controls, the researchers found that suicidal behavior was more prevalent in those who had poor attentional control. (Majid, Mahgol, & Taher, 2008) We employed an auditory optimum paradigm that was given in a non-active manner. Recording event-related potentials, or ERPs, which are assumed to represent processes involved with attention, was used to quantify the degree to which these "to be ignored" auditory stimuli were processed by the brain. In their study, Thompson and Chen Ong measured attentional bias and inhibition in two different Stroop tasks. (Thompson, Alonzo, Hu, & Hasin, 2017) This allowed them to evaluate the connection between suicidal conduct and neurological and behavioral indicators. High-risk individuals showed shorter reaction times in the Stroop analysis (as in the word "suicide") and decreased accuracy in their discordant trials. On the other hand, quicker response times were seen in the emotional Stroop task (with reduced activity in the left anterior regions). The findings demonstrated beyond a reasonable doubt that individuals who attempted suicide had attentional

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control abnormalities, which are thought to relate to circumstances of frontal asymmetry. Another major research was conducted by Hadlaczky and colleagues, who looked at the correlation between avoidance and suicidal tendencies in teenagers recruited from thirty schools located across seven different nations in Europe. After accounting for avoidance, depression, anxiety, and stress, as well as gender, attempts at suicide were able to be predicted in both cross-sectional and prospective studies that lasted for four months. Surprisingly, avoidance behavior did not serve as a reliable indicator of suicide thoughts in this population. (Eliason, 2009)

Clarification is needed about how these modifications evolve because of the individual's history of suicide and over their lifetime. The results of a study suggest that people who attempt suicide have a greater lack of fear of harm and death than controls who do not engage in suicidal behavior. This disparity may help to explain why males are more likely to die by suicide than women.

Methods

Taking up issues and seeking answers to such challenges those who have attempted suicide often struggle to find answers to their issues or strategies to deal with the stress they are under, or both. Notwithstanding this, the findings of several researches have frequently pointed to a relationship between suicidal behavior and inadequacies in both coping and the ability to resolve interpersonal conflicts. Having said that, given that most studies conducted on this topic are cross-sectional in nature, it is impossible to ascertain in which direction this relationship leads. In addition, the presence of melancholy is the major component that explains these relationships. (Ganz, Braquehais, & Sher, 2010). The connection between agitation and suicidal inclinations has been the subject of a considerable number of researches. A state of being that may be described as either disinhibited or worriedly excited is often referred to as agitation. For instance, a chart review of seventy-six patients who were found to have committed suicide upon admission revealed that 79 percent of them had been feeling severe anxiety or agitation in the days preceding up to their death. This was discovered when the patients' medical records were analyzed. It is a held belief that one of the pathways via which physical illness, the treatment of bipolar disorder, and the use of certain psychiatric drugs could elevate the patient's risk of suicide is agitation. This belief is supported by several studies. (Ganz, Braquehais, & Sher, 2010)

There is a need for more attention to be paid to the influence that the Internet has on suicidal behavior because it may have both negative (such as discouraging help-seeking) and positive (such as providing support resources or signs) impacts on suicidal conduct. Consequently, there is a need for more attention to be paid to the influence that the Internet has on suicidal behavior. The findings of

several researches indicate that about twenty percent of young people believe that the internet or social networking sites influence their decisions on whether to participate in behaviors that might result in self-inflicted harm. In addition, psychological mechanisms such as contagion, imitation, suggestion, identification, social learning, and classificatory homophily or susceptibility might play a role in the establishment of suicide clusters. It is well-established that social isolation and a lack of social support are significant predictors of the risk of suicide, and contemporary models of suicidal behavior often include these factors as major components. It is essential, if there is a chance of suicide, to determine the degree to which a sensitive individual is socially isolated. The topics of adverse life events, childhood adversities, and the occurrence of adverse life events in childhood followed by the experience of suicidal behavior are subjects that are the focus of separate areas of research. Some examples of adverse life events include physical, sexual, and emotional abuse; domestic violence; and (S.M, 2010). The findings of this study demonstrated that there is a statistically significant dose-response connection between the number of adverse events and the likelihood of further suicide attempts being made by the patient. Abuse in childhood, whether it be sexual or physical, is a behavior that has an especially significant danger. (Skelton, 2003)

Findings

An independent effort is required to concentrate on the psychological components that serve as a barrier to suicidal conduct. It is necessary to have a deeper comprehension of the psychological aspects of technique choice. More study in the field of psychology is very necessary in lifetime volunteers from a variety of nations and ethnic groups. It is vital to conduct clinical investigations that are both sufficiently large and sufficiently robust. It is essential to conduct clinical trials of psychological treatments to cut down on suicidal thoughts, attempts, and deaths. The development of more novel short psychosocial therapies (using a variety of delivery modalities) to minimize suicidal thoughts, attempts, and suicide is associated with an increased risk of suicidal and self-harming suicidal behavior as well as suicidal clusters. It is essential to have a deeper comprehension of the obstacles that prevent people from asking for assistance. The incorporation of recent advances in psychological science into programs for suicide prevention and intervention, as well as the development of public health interventions to foster resilience, are both important endeavors for low-income and middle-income countries. It is also important that interventions be developed. (Stevens, 2006)

Nevertheless, this study has been replicated by several different research groups, and the investigations conducted to far have not identified any preset treatments. The findings of a meta-analysis of cognitive behavioral therapies for suicidal behavior

showed a statistically significant effect of cognitive behavioral therapy for reducing the rate of suicide attempts; however, the researchers demonstrate a publication bias in this regard, with smaller studies reporting more positive effect sizes and no published study findings showing negative effects for any intervention. Regarding the prevention of at-risk individuals from attempting suicide, the findings of the meta-analysis showed a statistically significant effect of cognitive behavioral therapy for reducing the rate. A professional intervention known as collaborative evaluation and treatment of suicide aims to strengthen the therapeutic relationship and lower the risk of suicidal conduct among patients. In terms of safety planning measures, which include the identification of warning signals, coping methods, and support services, the restriction of access to potentially fatal paths is also acceptable. There has been some encouraging research done on the effectiveness of mentalization-based treatment in preventing self-harm in teenagers. (Kleespies, et al., 2011)

The DSM-5 does not include suicide as a diagnosis; nonetheless, the presence of a mental condition, particularly a mood disorder, is the single most crucial factor in determining one's likelihood of attempting suicide. Around ninety percent of those who die by suicide have been diagnosed with at least one mental illness, with mood disorders being the most prevalent of these conditions (Fleischman, Bertolote, Belfer, & Beautrais, 2005). As a matter of fact, the correlation between major depressive illness and suicide is so strong that, as was mentioned in earlier chapters, suicidal ideation is one of the requirements for diagnosis of the disease (APA, 2013). (Hepp, Wittmann, Schnyder, & Michel, 2004)

When a person contemplates terminating their own life but does not make any concrete plans to do so, they are said to be having suicidal thoughts. Most studies do not make a distinction between risk variables that are associated with having suicidal thoughts and risk factors that are associated with attempting suicide. Having a high pain tolerance and a low fear of death are both risk factors for attempting suicide, as opposed to merely having suicidal thoughts.

Discussion

Mental diseases, substance addiction, psychiatric problems, cultural, family, and societal circumstances, genetics, and experiences of trauma or loss are some of the factors that impact the likelihood of someone committing suicide. Substance misuse and mental illness are often seen together. Additional risk factors include having already attempted suicide, being in possession of the means necessary to end one's life, having a family history of suicide, or being in possession of a traumatic brain injury. For instance, research has shown that families containing guns have a greater suicide risk than households that are weapon-free. It is possible that issues in one's social and economic environment, such as unemployment, poverty,

homelessness, and prejudice, might cause suicide thoughts. It is possible that civilizations with great social cohesiveness and strong moral opposition to suicide have lower rates of suicide overall. Between 15 and 40 percent of those who die by suicide leave a note. The prevalence of mental illnesses such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and physical health problems that are directly connected to battle is one factor that contributes to the elevated suicide incidence among veterans of war. Genetics are responsible for somewhere between 38 and 55 percent of suicidal tendencies. It is also possible for there to be a cluster of suicides in a particular area. (Rozanov & Carli, 2012)

Those who have been hospitalized for suicidal conduct have an 8.6% chance of dying by suicide over their lives. In comparison, the lifetime risk of suicide among non-suicidal people hospitalized for mood disorders is much lower than in suicidal people.

It is 4%. Major depressive illness is thought to be present in around fifty percent of those who take their own lives; having this condition or any other mood disorder, such as bipolar disorder, raises the risk of suicide by a factor of twenty. (Suicide, 2017)

We acknowledge, for the sake of objectivity and fairness, that inpatient psychiatric treatment and the use of psychotropic medicines may be of assistance to a considerable number of suicidal individuals. The absence of suicidal-specific data, on the other hand, as was described before, is remarkable. To this aim, Jobes suggested that some modern clinicians may make assumptions about the effectiveness of inpatient treatment and drug use on the risk of suicide. Jobes' argument was since inpatient care and drug use are both often used. More crucially, such presumptions have the potential to have a considerable influence not only on the clinical condition of the patient but also on their whole life. Because of countertransference concerns or the fear of being sued if a patient takes their own life, a considerable number of physicians may find themselves not always acting in the best interest of their patients. This is a matter for great worry. On the other hand, concerns like these might result in behaviors that are excessively protective (for example, hospitalizing a patient with passive suicidal thoughts). Additionally, such practice habits may be formed by dreaming that remaining in the hospital for three to six days or treating mental problem with medicine is more beneficial than other treatments supported by research for suicide risk. (Pape & Review, 2003)

Hence, there may be a misperception that a "one-dimensional" treatment (that is, a brief hospitalization and medicine to treat the disease) would work for all suicidal people. Carol Dweck, a psychologist at Stanford University, proposed the idea of a psychological "mindset" in her work. This is another way to comprehend why some people may be so certain that these methods are successful. Dweck's empirical research has shown the presence of two

distinct mindsets, which she refers to as the "fixed" mentality and the "growth" mindset, respectively. Her study demonstrates how various mentalities are predictably associated to distinct results for one's personal and professional success, with a growth mindset being linked to outcomes that are much more adaptable and successful.

During the past two decades, clinical suicidology has seen several significant advancements, one of which may be the development and widespread application of various suicide-focused interventions. These interventions center on the preparation of stabilization plans in the event of potential acute suicidal crises. "Harmless Contracts" or "No Suicide" in sharp contrast to the persuasive and unpleasant usage of "contracts", several stabilization planning approaches for outpatient suicidal patients are intuitively more demanding and have proved helpful in clinical research trials. 48 Safety Plan, recognizing triggers, self-coping skills, distraction by others, supportive helps the patient through the steps to obtain assistance, acquire expert aid, and secure fatal roads. Many adopted the Safety Plan Intervention clinically early on as an intuitively preferable alternative for enforcing non-suicide contracts (despite the absence of factual justification for doing so) (despite the lack of empirical support for doing so). (Bertolote & Fleischmann, 2002)

Specifically, the death of a significant person would place survivors in a scenario where they are at an elevated risk for taking their own lives. Studies on those who have experienced bereavement have shown that the death rate is higher among surviving spouses. Individuals who have obvious dependence requirements will experience a heightened level of frustration in the aftermath of a loss since their security needs will have been disappointed concurrently. Necessarily, loss of a parent due to separation, divorce, sickness, or death in children or teenagers will function as a very high-risk factor for suicide. According to the findings of a research that looked at whether the death of a parent is a risk factor for suicide, patients who ended their own lives had much higher instances of maternal death than patients who did not end their own lives. In addition, it was discovered how old the patient was when he passed away, which was the age at which he had lost both of his parents. It is a statistically significant amount lower in the group that has attempted suicide compared to the group that has not attempted suicide. (Cerel, Jordan, & Duberstein, 2008)

An experience that brings up painful memories of a comparable occurrence from one's youth is associated with an elevated risk of taking one's own life. In addition to the actual loss of another significant person, threatening disappearances, loss of health, or even the loss of a national or cultural identification are believed to relate to an increased risk of suicide conduct. Family considerations it has been shown via empirical study that early and chronic life event stresses relate to suicide conduct, particularly when it occurs within the framework of a family. Many issues in the

relationships with members of the immediate family may come up in the time leading up to a suicide attempt. Insufficient levels of communication between parents and children have been demonstrated to be a potential contributory factor in a controlled research. In this research, the child and adolescent related to other characteristics such as family discord, a lack of family warmth, and damaged parent-child connections. On the other hand, psychopathology did not play a very major impact in people taking their own lives. (Kendall, 1983)

Suicide-scope: CC BY-SA²

There is a cluster of psychopathologies that are linked to suicidal behavior or attempts at suicide. These psychopathologies include aggression, drug addiction by parents or siblings, and antisocial personality disorder. It is not obvious if these family histories point to environmental pressures, a genetic propensity, or a mix of the two. The fact that a familial history of suicide as well as psychological variables were shown to enhance the probability of suicide is the most intriguing finding. Studies including families, twins, and adoption have all repeatedly shown that suicidal conduct tends to build in families. Attempts at suicide, particularly by mothers, were especially encouraged. Together with other characteristics such as fathers' drug use and family conflict, it is believed to be one of the biggest predictors of teenagers' attempts at suicide. If the observed family clustering is the result of the influence of common environmental variables or whether genetic factors play a role in the familial transmission of suicide. Furthermore, even after statistically controlling for the effect of parental

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psychopathology, family history of suicidal behavior was still found to be a significant risk factor. This suggests that the effect of family history of suicide is independent of the familial clustering that occurs in some families. (Friedman, Hrouda, Holden, Noffsinger, & Resnick, 2005)

Result

It is believed that the combination of the aforementioned factors might accurately and usefully predict future suicidal behavior in those who have attempted suicide in the past. There are over forty different risk factors that, when combined, may result in suicide behavior. For instance, a person with an active disorder (such as a mood or substance use disorder), who experiences a stressful event that is typically caused by an underlying condition (such as loss, humiliation, trouble with the law or school, etc.), may experience acute mood swings that lead to suicidal ideation. These acute mood swings include feelings of anxiety, hopelessness, and anger. In this stage, an underlying feature (such as impulsivity, for example) or a lack of social support may enhance suicidal thoughts, which in turn may progress to an actual act of suicide. In conclusion, it is essential to have an integrated understanding of the many elements that put a person at risk for suicide. At the micro level, clinicians need to consider not just the interactions that take place between the person and their family, but also the interactions that take place between the individual and the larger environmental setting. Along with the individual's mental or pathological states and biological vulnerability, psychosocial risk factors, such as acute or chronic stressors, suicidal facilitators, and background factors involved in suicide, should be considered in a comprehensive context. This is because these factors can all play a role in the decision to take one's own life. (Lapierre, et al., 2011)

In the field of psychology, the word "affect" has broadened its use beyond its previous confines in psychoanalysis and clinical psychiatry, and now refers to all subjective feelings (Tomkins, 1962). Affect, which was imposed by a metaphor from chemistry, is now generally acknowledged as being either positive or negative in terms of valence; the first connotes pleasurable sensations, and the second - unfavorable ones. The phrases "discontent" and "distress" are sometimes used interchangeably with "negative affect," but the words "stress" and "suffering" are occasionally also used to signify bad affect in general. (Kairys & Johnson, 2002)

Resources

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